

Hrebeniuk O.*Software Engineer, 24 and Up,**Raleigh, USA**ORCID ID: 0009-0003-0897-3579***Abstract**

The article examines architectural solutions used in the design of scalable next-generation ETL platforms under conditions of increasing data volume, velocity, and heterogeneity. It is shown that the transition from monolithic models to modular, microservices-based, and event-driven architectures is driven by the need to ensure horizontal scalability, fault tolerance, manageability, and data quality. The study analyzes the theoretical foundations of ETL platform design, modern architectural approaches, and key mechanisms for ensuring reliability, including orchestration, autoscaling, streaming processing, data quality control, and observability. It is concluded that an effective ETL platform should be viewed as a distributed and manageable environment combining technological flexibility, resilience, and cost efficiency.

Keywords: ETL platforms, scalability, data architecture, microservices architecture, streaming data processing, fault tolerance, data orchestration.

Introduction

Amid the rapid growth in data volume, variety, and generation speed, the architecture of extract, transform, and load platforms has become strategically important for the stable operation of digital ecosystems. While early corporate analytics relied mainly on centralized and relatively static data integration systems, such approaches are increasingly insufficient today. Increasing data sets, expanding cloud and hybrid infrastructures, the shift to streaming, and increased reliability requirements have created the need for rethinking traditional ETL (Extraction, Transformation, Loading) design principles. Scalable, flexible, manageable, and robust architectural solutions have thus emerged as key concepts.

Modern ETL platforms are no longer limited to data transfer between systems; they function as distributed software and infrastructure environments embedded in enterprise data management. Their effectiveness depends not only on the performance of individual components, but also on the ability of the overall architecture to adapt to changing workloads, support parallel

processing, maintain data consistency, and reduce failure risks. In this regard, special scientific interest is focused on the analysis of architectural models used in the development of the next generation of ETL platforms, such as monolithic, modular, microservices, and event-driven models.

The purpose of this study is to analyze the architectural models used in the development of scalable next-generation ETL tools, as well as the key mechanisms used for their efficiency, reliability, and flexibility.

Main part. Theoretical and technological foundations of building scalable ETL platforms

In general, an ETL platform is a software and architectural complex designed to extract data from heterogeneous sources, transform it according to predefined logic, and subsequently load it into target repositories, analytical data marts, or operational systems (fig. 1).

Figure 1. General architecture of an ETL platform [1]

In the modern context, ETL is no longer limited to scheduled linear batch processing; it functions as a distributed environment that must coordinate multiple data sources, support different processing modes, and remain manageable under continuously growing work-

loads [2]. For this reason, next-generation ETL platforms are increasingly viewed as part of a broader data management ecosystem, in which architectural properties are no less important than the functional capabilities of individual components.

The shift toward scalable ETL architectures is primarily driven by the changing scale of the digital environment. In addition, based on the Worldwide Global DataSphere Forecast (2024-2028) report by IDC, it is projected that the total global data created, captured, replicated, and consumed is expected to be 393.9 ZB by 2028, almost triple that of 2023. As data are distributed in cloud, edge, enterprise, and streaming environments, centralized integration approaches become less efficient, and horizontal scaling, distributed storage, and high-speed processing become critical for ETL platforms [3].

Under these conditions, the theoretical understanding of ETL platforms requires identifying the features that distinguish modern scalable solutions from traditional integration systems. While early ETL focused mainly on correct data transfer and load automation, contemporary platforms are defined by architectural properties that support distributed operation. These include horizontal scalability, support for multiple processing modes, loose coupling, flow manageability, observability, and built-in data quality control. Systematizing these characteristics helps clarify the technological nature of next-generation ETL platforms and provides a basis for further analysis of their architectural models (table 1).

Table 1.

Key characteristics of next-generation scalable ETL platforms

Characteristic	Description	Architectural significance
Distributed design	Data processing is performed across multiple interconnected services and infrastructure components rather than within a single execution node.	Enables high-volume data handling and reduces dependence on the limits of an individual server.
Horizontal scalability	Performance is increased by adding nodes, containers, or service instances instead of only expanding a single machine.	Supports workload growth without fundamental redesign of the platform.
Support for multiple processing modes.	The platform supports batch, near-real-time, and streaming scenarios all in one environment.	Broadens the applicability of ETL pipelines for analytical and operational workloads.
Modular structure	Extraction, transformation, loading, orchestration, monitoring, and validation are separated into relatively autonomous components.	Simplifies the maintenance, scaling, and evolution of the platform.
Loose coupling	Components interact through standardized interfaces, queues, or event-driven mechanisms.	Improves fault isolation and facilitates the integration of new sources and services.
Observability	The platform provides monitoring of execution states, resource utilization, pipeline behavior, and data anomalies.	Increases transparency of operations and accelerates fault detection and diagnosis.
Built-in data quality control	The validation rules, schema checks, consistency checks, and error handling are all integrated into the pipeline.	This ensures the reliability of the transformed data, reducing the possibility of error propagation into the target systems.

Therefore, the next-generation ETL platform should be viewed not as a collection of extraction, transformation, and loading procedures, but as an architecturally organized distributed system capable of operating reliably under growing workloads and increasing digital complexity. These characteristics demonstrate that the ETL architecture of today is no longer driven by the operations involved, but by the ability to facilitate scalability, manageability, reliability, and data quality.

Architectural approaches to the design of next-generation ETL platforms

In the context of ETL platforms, an architectural approach can be understood as a stable model for organizing components, data exchange channels, orchestration mechanisms, and scaling tools that determines system behavior under growing workloads, an increas-

ing number of data sources, and more complex processing scenarios [4]. For next-generation platforms, this issue is especially important, since ETL no longer functions as a local batch-loading tool but as a distributed digital infrastructure combining batch, near-real-time, and streaming scenarios in cloud or hybrid environments.

While the functional purpose remains the same, i.e., to extract, transform, and load the data, the way the components of the architectures interact, the way the workload is distributed, the way failure is handled, and the way the data flows are managed differ in various architectural models. Therefore, comparing architectural approaches makes it possible to identify those that best meet the requirements of the modern digital environment, including the rate at which the data is updated, the integration of the data sources, and the reliable operation in the distributed environment (table 2).

Main architectural approaches to the design of next-generation ETL platforms [5, 6]

Architectural approach	Description	Advantages	Limitations
Monolithic	All core ETL functions are implemented within a single unified system.	Simplicity of initial implementation, centralized control, lower complexity at early stages.	Limited scalability, high component interdependence, and difficulties in isolating failures and introducing changes.
Modular	ETL processes are divided into separate functional modules with limited autonomy.	Increased flexibility, easier maintenance, and selective scaling of subsystems.	Requires coordination between modules and standardization of interfaces.
Microservices-based	ETL functions are implemented as independent services with their own lifecycle.	High scalability, independent deployability, and improved fault isolation.	Increased operational complexity, as well as higher orchestration, monitoring, and DevOps needs.
Event-driven	Data processing is based on the concept of event streams, message queues, and asynchronous interactions.	Support for near-real-time processing, loose coupling, and high flexibility.	More complex consistency management, state handling, and end-to-end traceability.
Hybrid	Combines multiple architectural approaches within a single platform.	Flexibility in handling diverse workloads and a balance between scalability and stability.	More difficult architecture design, integration, and maintenance of system coherence.

The comparison illustrates that the development of next-generation ETL tools is accompanied by a gradual shift toward more flexible and distributed architectures, moving away from centralized and tightly coupled models. While monolithic architectures are applicable in limited and stable scenarios, modular, microservices-based, and event-driven architectures are more appropriate in scenarios with growing workloads, various data sources, and complex processing scenarios. Nevertheless, the choice of architecture depends on various factors, such as data and processing characteristics, as well as organizational maturity, which is why hybrid architectures that leverage the best features of each approach within a single integration tool are becoming increasingly relevant.

Overall, current trends in the development of architectural solutions for high-performance ETL platforms are associated with increasing distribution, the growing role of event-driven models, deeper integration of orchestration and observability, and the shift toward hybrid architectures that combine batch and streaming processing within a unified environment. Platform decomposition into autonomous services capable of scaling independently according to workload profile is becoming increasingly important, while transport and orchestration layers are gradually turning into core elements of the entire ETL environment. At the same time, the importance of architectural solutions focused on fault tolerance, processing reproducibility, data quality control, and cost-efficient use of infrastructure resources is increasing, reflecting the transition of ETL from a set of technical procedures to a fully developed high-load digital platform.

Key mechanisms for ensuring the scalability and reliability of ETL platforms

The scalability and reliability of next-generation ETL platforms depend not only on the choice of architecture, but also on a set of engineering mechanisms that enable the system to adapt to growing workloads, isolate failures, preserve data integrity, and maintain predictable recovery time. In distributed environments, these properties must be ensured simultaneously at the computational, transport, orchestration, and data quality levels. Therefore, ETL platforms should be analyzed not only in terms of their overall architecture, but also through the specific technical mechanisms that provide elasticity, fault tolerance, and operational stability [7].

The first key mechanism is **horizontal scaling of computational components**. In modern ETL tools, increasing performance is not done by increasing the capacity of a single node but instead done by adding multiple instances of parallel services. This is the same idea behind the Kubernetes Horizontal Pod Autoscaler, which scales the number of replicas of a Pod based on certain metrics. In ETL, this is important because there are usually varied loads in stages such as ingestion, transformation, validation, and loading. As a result, architectural resilience depends on the ability to scale bottlenecks rather than the entire system.

The practical importance of autoscaling is confirmed by modern cloud data platforms. For example, Google Cloud Dataflow is a fully managed service for batch and streaming data processing, supporting autoscaling for both types of pipelines. It can scale up to 4,000 workers per job, and petabytes of data are regularly processed. For ETL platforms, this shows that horizontal scaling is no longer experimental but a standard operating mode, improving both throughput and cost efficiency.

The second important mechanism is the **decomposition of processing through message brokers and streaming buses**. By introducing an intermediate transport layer between data producers and consumers, the platform can absorb load spikes, decouple component lifecycles, and reprocess data without blocking the entire pipeline. In this context, delivery and processing guarantees are especially important. For example, Apache Kafka provides durable event storage in topics and supports exactly-once processing semantics, which allows scalable ETL pipelines to avoid unnecessary duplication and preserve result consistency during retries, intermediate failures, and asynchronous execution.

The importance of the transport layer is also demonstrated by vendor benchmarks. In Google Cloud Managed Service for Apache Kafka, increasing producer batch size from 1 KB to 10 KB raised throughput from 48,049 to 160,694 messages per second while reducing latency from 608 to 171 ms. Similarly, increasing consumer fetch size from 10 KB to 500 MB improved throughput from 2.7 to 60 MB/s [8]. Although these results are environment-specific, they highlight a key point: ETL performance depends not only on compute capacity, but also on proper configuration of buffering, batching, and parallel data exchange.

The third mechanism is **fault-tolerant processing through checkpointing, replay, and exactly-once or at-least-once delivery policies**. This is essential for streaming ETL platforms, where even a short failure

under high input rates can cause data loss or duplication. For example, Google Cloud Dataflow officially supports exactly-once record processing while maintaining low latency. In practice, this means that ETL reliability depends not only on infrastructure redundancy, but also on processing semantics that allow safe re-execution without compromising data integrity.

Operational reliability is closely linked to formally defined availability targets. For example, Google Cloud Dataflow specifies a Service Level Agreement with a Monthly Uptime Percentage of at least 99.9%. Although an SLA does not guarantee faultlessness of a particular pipeline, it does define an important engineering principle for next-generation ETL tools: these tools must be designed for continuous operation, where failures are considered normal and must be automatically recoverable. This suggests that these tools should be equipped with retry mechanisms and be capable of resuming execution from partial failures.

The fourth key mechanism is **mature task orchestration**. Unlike traditional schedulers, modern orchestrators coordinate dependencies between pipeline stages, manage retries, separate control and execution logic, and provide observability of DAG processes. The practical importance of this layer is supported by industry data: according to The State of Airflow 2025, 47.9% of respondents already consider Airflow to be business-critical (fig. 2).

Figure 2. Airflow adoption in business-critical and large-scale production environments [9]

These indicators show that the orchestration layer has evolved into a fully critical subsystem of large ETL platforms rather than merely a supporting interface for task execution.

The fifth mechanism is platform **observability and data quality control**. According to Precisely (2025), 76% of organizations have already implemented formal observability programs for data quality and pipelines. At the same time, the dbt Labs 2025 report shows that 38% of teams plan to increase investments in data quality and observability, while 56% of respondents explicitly identify data quality as a problem. This is particularly important for ETL platforms, where, as the number of sources and transformations grows, failures may appear not as system outages but as “silent” data degradation, including staleness, missing values, duplicates, schema violations, and data drift. Therefore, ETL reliability should be understood

beyond infrastructure availability and include the system’s ability to detect quality deviations in a timely manner.

Thus, the scalability and reliability of next-generation ETL platforms are ensured by a combination of interrelated mechanisms, including horizontal scaling, automatic resource allocation, streaming transport layers, exactly-once semantics, mature orchestration, and advanced observability [10]. Recent studies show that it is the integration of these mechanisms, rather than the isolated use of any single tool, that enables ETL platforms to maintain performance, correctness, and manageability under increasing data sources, more complex transformations, and the transition to near-real-time processing.

Conclusion

Architectural solutions for next-generation scalable ETL platforms are shaped by key technological shifts, including the rapid growth of data volume and velocity, the adoption of cloud-native infrastructures,

the expansion of streaming processing, and increasing data quality requirements. In this context, traditional monolithic ETL models lose effectiveness, while modular, microservices-based, and event-driven architectures offer greater scalability, flexibility, and resilience for modern distributed environments.

At the same time, the efficiency of an ETL platform as a distributed environment depends not only on architecture but also on the maturity of underlying engineering mechanisms such as horizontal scaling, dynamic resource allocation, streaming transport layers, reliable processing semantics, and so on. Hence, the next generation of ETL platforms should be designed as distributed and managed environments, where flexibility is combined with reliability, reproducibility, and efficiency.

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